

Names of Diseases in the Vernacular

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Abstract. *Illness is a reaction of some parts of the body to damage, infection or other factors. A non-terminological name of a disease is a word or phrase associated with a non-terminological (everyday) medical lexicon, that is, synonymous with the scientific names of diseases and widely used in colloquial speech. used anemia - anemia, hepatitis - jaundice, Kreittfelidt - Jakob - cow rabies (brain decay), hallucination - delirium, vitiligo - pes, tuberculosis - tuberculosis, epilepsy - seizure, acne - dysentery, parotitis - reaction to the group of speech units or archaism Past words: hemorrhoids, diarrhea, heartburn.*

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Enter. The role of the mother tongue in reflecting the identity, worldview, way of life, past and future of a particular nation is incomparable. As a result of the practical use of the linguistic possibilities of the language, the study of the connection of linguistics with a number of disciplines, the fluency of the speech was clearly demonstrated. The creative function and practical importance of language was revealed as a result of the integration of linguistics with a number of disciplines. As a result, a number of branches of linguistics were formed: psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, neurolinguistics, linguoculturology, medical linguistics, etc.

Everyone is prone to illness. A disease derived from the Latin word *morbus* (synonym - illness, illness) is a state of the body. According to the dictionary, it is a pathological process that occurs when the body is affected by harmful factors of the external or internal environment. The disease affects the adaptation of a person to the changing conditions of the external and internal environment, and affects the health of a person. The word "disease" in a broad sense is any open or hidden, momentary or permanent, deviation from the normal state, which certainly affects the appearance of a person, the characteristics of his behavior. Illness is a reaction of some parts of the body to damage, infection or other factors. There are many causes of the disease, which allows them to be classified in different ways:

1) congenital diseases; 2) infectious diseases; 3) metabolic diseases; 4) tumor diseases; 5) diseases caused by chemical effects, poisoning; 6) degenerative diseases; 7) allergic diseases, etc.

The non-terminological names of diseases that are a part of the linguistic image of the world of Uzbek speakers and reflect human knowledge of medicine have been formed since ancient times. In the course of research, it is known that in the modern scientific medical discourse, real non-terminological names of diseases, their composition and national characteristics are paid little attention, these words are not analyzed specifically, but are considered only within the framework of other problems.

The entire set of lexemes belonging to this group is very unique, the introduction of the foreign language element mainly coincides with the 19th-20th centuries, when the pressure of internationalism increased, and despite this, the lexicon under consideration shows great resistance: modern medical a significant number of ancient formations have been preserved in the way of life (measles, smallpox, chicken pox, cancer, hernia, hernia, etc.). For this reason, the structure of disease names is very stable and deeply archaic. The names of diseases are closely related to this context, and they logically follow from it. It is either a word that corresponds to the name of a body part, or, in most cases, a noun formed from a verb that corresponds to a verb that describes the patient's condition or the external causes of that condition. For example: hernia, constipation, goiter, diarrhoea, pruritus, uraz, uroch, pestilence, small pox, shingles, muscle contraction, muteness, anemia, fainting, suffocation, swelling, eye contact, back colic, nausea, shock, back pain and many others.

Terms appear in the language on the basis of universal laws (derivation, semantic transfer, metonymization) and others. In the formation and development of the terminology of the Uzbek language, it is possible to observe the formation of many medical terms through metaphor. Usually, a term (from the Latin "terminus" - "limit", "boundary mark") is a word or combination of words that clearly expresses the concept of something related to science, technology and other fields, and the scope of use is limited to these fields. Terms differ from common words in terms such as being unambiguous, lacking in expressiveness and emotionality. As in all lexical resources of the Uzbek language, the terms have their own ways of enrichment and they correspond to the general laws of the development of our language. There is not a single language in the world that has not acquired foreign words. In order to express a new concept in all languages, either a ready-made term from another language is adopted, or a word or term existing in this language is used, or a new term is created. Including, the medical terminology that we are going to talk about has also passed its great development path. According to terminologists, metaphor plays the main role in the formation of a term in the semantic method. In this case, such new terms are created due to the fact that they are similar in form and color of the words of common literary or living language. In many works dedicated to the study of the terminological systems of various fields of the Uzbek language, term formation using the semantic method is recognized as an important source of terminology enrichment. However, when researching medical terms, the terms in which the metaphor is considered the main tool appeared mainly by the semantic-syntactic method. It is known that in the enrichment of medical terminology, which began to be formed from very ancient times, the formation of terms in a semantic way has been used. By the beginning of the 20th century, with the formation and rapid development of cognitive linguistics, it was recognized that metaphor is a multifaceted, extremely complex phenomenon, and its essence as a manifestation of fundamental cognitive activity was revealed. Metaphor is an effective way of forming medical terms. Metaphors are also very useful in creating medical terms. Medicinally, scurvy, tympanic membrane, cornea, black eye, chicken pox, small pox, tetanus, tetanus, eyeball, fish coin, earlobe, nasopharyngeal conch, auricular conch, the use of terms such as urethra is directly related to the metaphor. Modern medical terminology is one of the most complex in the system of terms. It contains thousands of words and phrases. One of the most productive ways to create a term is metaphor. Metaphor is one of the main methods of pictorial representation of reality and reflects a certain linguistic image of the world in terminology. The universal feature of a metaphor is that it exists in the mind of any person, regardless of what language they speak. Medical terminology is one of the specific layers of word combinations that differ from ordinary words by their structural, semantic, word-forming and stylistic features, and thus occupy a special place in the lexical system of the language. Non-terminological name of the disease means a word or phrase associated with non-terminological (everyday) medical vocabulary. These are words that are synonymous with the scientific names of diseases, are variants and are widely used in colloquial speech, or are not actively used in everyday speech, and have passed into the category of archaisms. These nominations can be found in etymological dictionaries, a dictionary of historical words, a medical encyclopedia, an explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, as well as in the texts of examples of folklore (epics, legends...) or often in special medical will be recorded in terminological and philological dictionaries.

From time immemorial, mankind has always been concerned with problems related to health and prolonging life, diagnosis and treatment of diseases, and in accordance with this, medical units were formed and began to occupy an important place in the lexical system of the language. For example, in medicine related to the era of the founder of the Uzbek language, A. Navoi, various names are found in the field of eye diseases: illusion - the appearance of objects such as mosquitoes and flies in front of the eyes. If it is from stomach steam, the sign is: increase in stomach during fullness, indigestion. For example:

When a vision approaches each eye,

There will be a hundred disasters and conspiracies in his ambush.

If it is caused by stomach fumes,

Look for a solution, that will be the cure.

Only eye diseases related to leprosy (thickening of the eyelids, redness and loss of eyelashes), gabr (an ulcer that protrudes into the corner of the eye on the side of the nose), turfa (in the discharge of the eye) like a red or blue dot; subot related to head diseases - extremely heavy sleep, humqu ri'wanat - mental disorder, heaviness of the head and excessive sleep, medical terminology such as sarsam, i.e. swelling of one or both of the two membranes that surround the brain there is a layer of lexical units that do not have a place in the system, and their separate research is one of the tasks facing the onomasiology field of linguistics. In addition, the generally accepted colloquial names of some phenomena related to human health do not leave linguists indifferent in every era.

Russian linguists such as G. A. Abramova, E. A. Akimova, N. E. Mazalova, V. T. Katerinich, V. A. Merkulova, A. V. Yudin were very interested in the study of medical lexical units. For example, E. A. Akimova studies the non-terminological names of diseases from a linguistic and cultural point of view, focusing on the study of motives based on the names of the concepts of folk medicine, and the researcher analyzes the cognitive aspect of naming. The researches of N.E. Mazalova and V.T. Katerinich are aimed at studying the relationship between the religious-mystical views of Russian speakers and the vocabulary of folk medicine, while V.T. Katerinich studied folk and terminological names of diseases, body parts, drugs, and the emergence of such designations. considered the sources of being. V.A. Merkulova studied the origin of the folk lexicon belonging to the semantic field of medicine, compared the non-terminological names of diseases used in Russian with similar names in other Slavic languages, and identified a number of terminological definitions of diseases and phenomena related to them. Explained the meanings of the names of the A.V. Yudin developed a complete description of the corpus of magical, magical names related to healing in Russian folklore texts, showing the universal sorcerer and witch characters, their assistants, diviners, protectors (healers) and all their functions.

It can be said that G.A. Abramova's dissertation on the medical lexicon, its main features and development trends was one of the big steps in the study of the medical vocabulary layer. This study is the result of excellent research on the synchronic and diachronic description of scientific medical terminology and commonly used medical lexicon.

A number of scientists such as A. Husanov, A. Kasimov, Z. Mirakhmedova, H. Dadaboev, A. Madvaliyev, Y. Torakulov have contributed greatly to the history and formation of medical terminology in Uzbek linguistics.

So, it is clear from the above that in Russian linguistics and Turkic studies, the lexical-semantic system related to folk medicine, illness and health has been studied in detail. Linguistic, etymological, ethnographic, communicative aspects of medical units are analyzed in researches in this field. However, the modern scientific aspect of the original non-terminological names of diseases, their composition and functions has received little attention, these words have not been specifically analyzed, but only considered in the context of other problems.

Anon-terminological name of a disease is a word or phrase associated with a non-terminological (everyday) medical lexicon, that is, synonymous with the scientific names of diseases and widely

used in colloquial speech. used anemia - anemia, hepatitis - jaundice, Kreittfelidt-Jakob - cow rabies (brain decay), hallucination - delirium, vitiligo - pes, tuberculosis - tuberculosis, epilepsy - seizure, acne - dysentery, parotitis - reaction to speech units or archaism series Past words: hemorrhoids, diarrhea, heartburn.

We can see that the names we are studying, which are used in the everyday speech of people without medical education, are widely used in philological dictionaries. For example, insanity, lupus, yawning, hiccups, scabies, bone worms, night blindness, anemia, scabies.

Non-terminological names of diseases are closely related to international medical scientific names. In medicine, the existence of non-terminological medical units, which are used side by side with international, that is, scientific terms, is considered a sociolinguistic problem, and at the same time, it is inextricably linked with the speech ethics of doctors. Because in order to understand the patient, it is necessary to replace the medical term with a non-terminological name. This encourages the doctor to be aware of both international and national names of medical units. Why should you be aware of medical-national options? When you go to the doctor and say that you have a heart attack, the young specialist does not know the term in the vernacular and prescribes drugs for heart pain. It is said that an experienced doctor who walks among the people, often refers to dictionaries, and knows the meaning of terms, sees the patient's condition, changes the diagnosis and recommends anti-diarrhea remedies.

A doctor must use international nomenclature and terms in making a diagnosis, in official documents, medical references, as well as in communication with colleagues (consiliums). However, when communicating with a patient, a doctor must have sufficient verbal skills and vocabulary to explain diseases and the possible consequences of the disease to a person who is far from the medical profession. In the speech, it is necessary to use the everyday version of the basic medical unit, the popular form used in the vernacular: "You have pneumonia, which is a consequence of infection with the corona virus, that is, inflammation of the lungs. The disease developed against the background of chronic bronchitis"; "You have epilepsy, which is one of the most common chronic neurological diseases. Epilepsy is caused by brain swelling," etc.

Thus, a more comprehensive study of the non-terminological names of diseases allows to present them as a part of the linguistic image of the world of Uzbek speakers, which reflects human knowledge about medicine.

REFERENCES:

1. Абу Али ибн Сино. Уржуза ёки 1326 байт таҳлили. Тошкент: Абу Али ибн Сино номидаги тиббиёт нашриёти-1999. -Б.160
2. Abuzalova M., Islomova Sh. Tibbiyot tili va tibbiy matnlarning psixolingvistik xususiyatlari \ O'zbekiston milliy universiteti xabarlari, 2023, [1/4] ISSN 2181-7324
3. https://vaqt.ucoz.com/publ/tibbiyot/tibbiyotdagi_rivojlanish_davrlari/10-1-0-961
4. Зайцев Г. К. Валеолого-педагогические основы обеспечения здоровья человека в системе образования: Автореф. дис. д-ра. пед. наук / С.- Петерб. ун-т пед. мастерства. - СПб, 1998. - 48 с.
5. Г. Л. Микиртичан Врачи и музыка \ Церковь и медицина № 2 (16). 06 Апреля 2017.
6. Г. Л. Микиртичан Врачи и музыка \ Церковь и медицина № 2 (16). 06 Апреля 2017.
7. Islomova Sh. Tibbiyot va she'riyat mushtarakligi \ Til, ta'lim, tarjima xalqaro jurnal 2022. 3-son, 6-jild.